

1 Indian parliamentary panel’s recommendations on
2 cancer prevalence and prevention with response of the
3 government: A commentary.
4
5

6 **Authors:**

- 7 1. Raja Singh*, Department of Environmental and Occupational Health, Dornsife
8 School of Public Health, Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA, USA.
9
- 10 2. Ashish Jakhetiya, Department of Surgical Oncology, Geetanjali Medical College and
11 Hospital, Udaipur, India.
12
- 13 3. Abhijeet V Jadhav, National Institute of Virology (Indian Council of Medical
14 Research), Pune, India.
15
- 16 4. Tarang Patel, Department of Pathology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences,
17 Rajkot, India.
18
- 19 5. Kanwalpreet Kaur, Department of Pathology, Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate
20 Medical Research, Puducherry, India.
21
- 22 6. Arthur L Frank, Department of Environmental and Occupational Health, Dornsife
23 School of Public Health, Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA, USA.

24 ***Corresponding author:** rs3788@drexel.edu , rajaresearch@proton.me

25 **Abstract**

26
27 This commentary looks at the recommendations in two chapters related to the
28 incidence, prevention, screening, early detection, and diagnosis of cancer cases
29 that were recommended by India’s legislative branch to India’s executive branch
30 in the form of 33 recommendations. These dealt with issues related to robust
31 recordkeeping of cancer disease and mortality data, tobacco cessation, screening
32 for cancers its’ integration into the public health insurance scheme of India. This
33 commentary informs regarding these recommendations by the parliamentary
34 committee on health to the health ministry as it paves the way for action on cancer
35 epidemiology and prevention in India.
36

37 **Keywords:** *registry, cervical cancer, tobacco cessation, notification, health*
38 *policy, Modicare*
39
40

1 The Indian parliament, under the Rajya Sabha, or upper house, released a report
2 titled ‘Cancer Care Plan & Management: Prevention, Diagnosis, Research &
3 Affordability of Cancer Treatment’ which was the culmination of years of work
4 by the Department-related parliamentary standing committee on health and
5 family welfare in response to the ‘growing burden of cancer in India’^{1,2}. India,
6 being a democracy has branches of governance, with the legislature, the
7 executive, and the judiciary. The legislature, through the parliament, has the
8 power to provide recommendations to the government or the executive branch
9 (the ministries) and these can be scrutinised by the judiciary. These checks and
10 balances provide governance which prevents any one branch, mostly the
11 executive, from overstepping their power and authority and protects
12 fundamental rights of India’s citizens. A matter reaching a parliamentary
13 committee’s attention highlights the public interest importance of the matter, the
14 lengthy deliberation needed for the matter, and it also means the parliament
15 wants to exercise its privilege to check on the executive as a ‘watch dog’ (or
16 provide oversight). For this particular issue, the scope was widened by the
17 committee from mere affordability of treatment to include ‘management,
18 prevention, diagnosis, research’ and to create a plan for the same^{1,3}.
19 The report had eight chapters and 158 recommendations. Various stakeholders
20 were summoned to interact with the committee. After the release, the Ministry
21 of Health, and Family Welfare (MoHFW) of the Government of India responded
22 to the report of this committee and provided a reply in four categories. The
23 response of the government has been published as a stand-alone report⁴. Out of
24 158 recommendations, 57 were accepted by the ministry. 45 recommendations
25 were categorised as ones which the committee did not ‘desire to pursue in view
26 of the Ministry’s replies.’ 39 are ones which the committee did not accept and
27 provided further recommendations⁴. There are 17 recommendations in respect
28 of which the final replies from the MoHFW have not been received.
29 This commentary looks at the Recommendations in Chapter one and Chapter
30 two of the report which are related to ‘Incidence of Cancer cases’ and
31 ‘Prevention, Screening, Early detection, and Diagnosis of cancer cases’
32 respectively. The primary focus of this commentary is to understand the
33 situation with respect to cancer prevalence and prevention in India. A total of 33
34 recommendations have been made in these two chapters. The authors have also

1 tried to critically present recommendations and their responses in a simplified
2 manner to interpret any gaps or highlights.
3 Of 158, a total of 33 recommendations have been studied along with their
4 response by the MoHFW and have been summarised in Table 1. The authors
5 have summarised the main idea behind the recommendation and the response
6 from the government together and summarised it in a single column. Out of the
7 33 recommendations discussed, 14 are the ones which are accepted by the
8 MoHFW, 13 are the ones which the committee did not wish to pursue after
9 response from the MoHFW and 6 are the ones for which the committee was not
10 satisfied with the response from the ministry and stressed on giving further
11 recommendations.

12 The committee provided a comprehensive report, and the first two chapters
13 include various areas which can be broadly classified into seven major
14 categories which are: **1. Tobacco cessation, 2. Human Papilloma Virus**
15 **(HPV) vaccination 3. Steps related to data capturing, robust recordkeeping,**
16 **reporting and notification of cancer cases and deaths, 4. Preventive**
17 **screening of cancers at population scale, 5. Awareness related to cancer**
18 **prevention and control, 6. Enhancing hospital infrastructure and**
19 **mechanisms under the Ayushman Bharat Program (India’s Public Health**
20 **Insurance Scheme), and 7. Finance related initiatives for individuals.** There
21 are other related issues which were also addressed.

22 Looking at the six recommendations which the committee stressed despite a
23 response from the government, four out of which were related to the issue of
24 cancer recordkeeping by creation of an unbiased registry, gathering actual
25 mortality data enhancing the coverage of the National Cancer Registry Program
26 (NCRP) and inclusion of the Ayushman Bharat hospitals (which are hospitals
27 under the *Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana*, or PM-JAY also called the
28 *Ayushman Bharat Yojana*) into the registry. PM-JAY is the national public
29 health insurance scheme of the Government of India which is also colloquially
30 called “Modicare”. Of the rest, one was related to the issue of tobacco cessation
31 and disincentivising tobacco use by taxing it to the highest possible rate. The
32 last was related to screening of cancers for prevention and early diagnosis which
33 the committee reiterated must become a ‘people’s mass movement’ with one
34 day in each month declared for the same.

1 There were 14 recommendations of the committee that were accepted by
2 MoHFW. These include two recommendations regarding operationalising HPV
3 vaccinations and making them part of the universal immunisation program of
4 India. Five recommendations were related to awareness related to cancer in
5 India. This includes prevention related initiatives through the ‘Eat Right’
6 campaign, food safety standards, creation of community-based assessment
7 checklists and disseminating information. There was also focus in three
8 recommendations on strengthening the PM-JAY⁵. The committee spoke about
9 implementation of the operational framework for management of cancers
10 through the PM-JAY hospitals, need for improvement in a trust deficit in
11 government hospitals, inclusion of private hospitals, along with training staff in
12 these hospitals ⁶. One committee recommendation was on a common patient
13 identifier and linking it to Ayushman Bharat with another related to screening of
14 cancers which the government stated was operational since 2016-18. Three
15 recommendations were around epidemiology and recordkeeping and involved
16 linking Ayushman Bharat hospitals to the National Cancer Registry Program,
17 linking data from diagnostics to treatment by involving common patient
18 identifiers and doing research which would understand regional and urban-rural
19 heterogeneity of data.
20 Finally, there were 13 recommendations which the committee did not ‘wish to
21 pursue in view of’ the replies by the MoHFW. This can be assumed to mean that
22 the committee was content with the response of the ministry and did not stress
23 upon the recommendations any further. These included four recommendations
24 related to tobacco cessation, including reduction of the prevalence of tobacco
25 use which is strategized to have been reduced by 30% by 2025 as per the
26 National Health Policy 2017 ⁷. The recommendations included prohibition on
27 chewable tobacco, campaigning against tobacco use and focus on tobacco and
28 alcohol use in the North-eastern states of India. Five recommendations were
29 related to robust recordkeeping of cancer cases and related issues. These, apart
30 from making cancer a notifiable disease to prevent underreporting of cancer,
31 include getting correct regional and hotspot epidemiological information. This
32 also included having national level surveys include the parameters related to a
33 cancer management framework, like asking for screening data in census related
34 surveys. Two recommendations were related to expansion of screening beyond

1 oral, breast and cervical cancers and stressed similar policy programs and make
2 it population based rather than opportunity based. This means that currently
3 screening is often done when patients come for other care, but this would make
4 screening a primary mission. Two important recommendations were related to
5 financial incentives such as marginal concessions in health insurance for people
6 who take screening and for capping patient fees for diagnostic tests.
7 It is important to understand that the committee stressed two areas of
8 recommendations. One being robust recordkeeping, notification and enhancing
9 and expanding the registry of cancer and the second being tobacco cessation.
10 Other important areas were screening of cancers and awareness of cancer and
11 prevention related information.
12 Limitations in this commentary include the fact that the Table 1 is a simplified
13 version of the actual report, and the classification uses generalisation to classify
14 recommendations into seven broad categories as mentioned before.
15 There may be some suggestions that may be important from the point of view of
16 prevention of cancer and understanding its prevalence in India.
17 Foremost, is making cancer notifiable in India, which will enable a legal
18 framework so that all the cases of cancer that reach a medical practitioner are
19 reported to a government registry. It may be argued that by simple creation of a
20 registry, without having a legal mandate to report disease would automatically
21 result in better cancer recordkeeping, but the fact is that India already has a
22 voluntary, non-mandatory registry which has been operating since 1981, but
23 covers only 16% of India's population at present ⁸. Enhanced recordkeeping
24 would lead to better understanding of the causation, geographical hotspots,
25 gender disparity, urban-rural disparity and regional disparities ⁹.
26 There have been studies which document non reporting or underreporting of
27 cases related to occupational cancers caused, for example, by asbestos, despite
28 required mandatory reporting (in some cases there were reports in academic
29 papers but not to regulators, as mandated by law) ^{10,11}.
30 Further, it is imperative that prevention of avoidable cancers must be undertaken
31 so that the future burden and expense of disease can be reduced. This may
32 require giving up some revenue generation through tobacco, and similar
33 carcinogens like asbestos going forward ¹². However, cancer prevention over
34 time will recoup all such lost revenue through not needing care of future cases.

1 Also, ‘almost all cervical cancer cases are linked to infection with high-risk
2 HPV, an extremely common virus transmitted through sexual contact’ means
3 that it needs similar attention as other communicable diseases which have
4 potential community spread ^{13,14}.
5 Another important suggestion is dealing with tobacco related cancer incidence
6 in the country. This involves making the anti-tobacco law , i.e., The Cigarettes
7 and Other Tobacco Products (Prohibition of Advertisement and Regulation of
8 Trade and Commerce, Production, Supply and Distribution) Act, 2003 or the
9 COTPA Act 2003 more stringent with stricter penalties ¹⁵. The current 200
10 rupees penalty (1-3 USD) is not a string deterrent and is often not implemented
11 ¹⁶. Tax based disincentivising must be done. The issue to which the ministry did
12 not directly respond is the high use of alcohol along with tobacco in the North-
13 eastern states, which may be culturally sensitive, but needs priority attention.
14 There is also the issue of smoked meat highlighted by the committee in these
15 states which can be looked at scientifically without any cultural or political
16 consequence regarding public health of this area ¹⁷.
17 A simplified, point by point analysis of all 33 recommendations is given in
18 Table 1.
19 The overall discussion in India around cancer can be summarised by two
20 common adages: ‘*Whatever that can be measured, can be managed*’ and
21 ‘*Prevention is better than cure*’.
22
23
24
25

Table 1: Summary of recommendations listed in the report by the parliamentary committee along with the MoHFW reply and remarks of the authors.

S. No.	Recommendation Number as per original report.	Summary of the recommendation and the MoHFW reply simplified by authors	Broad Area of the Recommendation-Simplified (classified by authors)	Remarks by authors.
<i>Summary of recommendations accepted by MoHFW</i>				
1	1.5.9	Linking of all empanelled hospitals under Ayushman Bharat with NCDIR cancer registry database will be done.	Recordkeeping	An important step as many hospitals are not part of the NCRP and by inclusion, fuller data can be captured. Other large private hospitals currently not part of Ayushman Bharat, and not part of the NCRP, must be included.
2	1.9.3	To understand regional heterogeneity and rural vs. urban disparities, the research for the same must be focussed which will be done by the National Cancer Centre under AIIMS Delhi.	Recordkeeping	The action of making cancer notifiable and getting every institute under coverage will enable such research to take place, as data will be the foundation for the same. If cancer registry is maintained such data will

				be automatically available and facilitate epidemiological studies.
3	2.2.3	Screening for cancer and prevention was advised which the government says has been operational by the Comprehensive Primary Health Centre since 2016 and by Ayushman Bharat Wellness Centres since 2018.	Screening	Screening currently only covers oral, breast and cervical cancer. Special exposure groups can be identified, including for occupational cancers, or life style related cancers
4	2.3.2	The recommendation involved HPV vaccine, which the government has recommended twice, in 2017 and 2022, to be made part of the universal vaccination program by the National Technical Advisory Group on Immunisation in India (NTAGI).	HPV Vaccine	Cervical cancer causation is linked to HPV which commonly spreads through close sexual contact. This can mean that there is a likelihood of community spread and making cancer notifiable will help by providing the right data on cancers.
5	2.3.3	The committee stressed awareness activities to which the government stated that government is running programs like 'Fit India', national cancer day, primary health centres and school based 'health and wellness ambassadors'. There has been creation of 'Community Based Assessment Checklist' filled by Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA) workers.	Awareness	The implementation of the programs and their regular audit may be needed to carry good intentions into universal practice.
6	2.3.5	The NTAGI recommended including HPV vaccine in 2017 and in 2022 but due to a Supreme Court case, this has been delayed.	HPV Vaccine	Since these cases are over now, there can be beginning of implementation of this vaccination under Universal Immunisation Program or UIP. Resource allocation to the program can be challenge. Currently it is focused only for adolescent girls whereas in developed nations boys are also covered.

				The government is acting to roll out the vaccine.
7	2.3.6	Youth awareness movements like 'Eat Right India' initiative, front of pack nutrition and the food regulator notified school food safety standards which prohibit sales of food with high added saturated fat, sodium, and sugar. The committee also raised the issue of smoked meat issue in North-east India which was not addressed by the government but included in the general answer.	Awareness	These well intentioned programs must be regularly audited for their actual implementation. The issue of smoked meat must be addressed in a culturally sensitive manner detached from a political angle.
8	2.4.1	Patients approaching private hospitals due to a trust deficit in government hospitals raised by the committee was addressed by the government by stating that new tertiary care as well as other hospitals with a distributed cancer care model was being adopted.	Ayushman Bharat	Under the Ayushman Bharat Scheme, all hospitals, both private and public, may be governed by the same rates, and this may create competition for public hospitals to compete for patient care with private hospitals. This may degrade the ability of government hospitals to take care of complex cases, hence, the push for high end public tertiary care hospitals may be needed, as it strengthens the tertiary level referral-based system. For the distributed cancer care model, the strengthening of primary care is a step in the right direction.
9	2.6.4	Implementation of the operational framework for management of common cancers was stressed.	Ayushman Bharat	Operational framework is in the right direction, and this needs a separate analysis, which is beyond the scope of this commentary.

10	2.9.2	The committee recommended training of frontline health care staff and physicians on the detection of red flags of cancer and a course indicating clear clinical pathways in detection or treatment. The committee also suggested streamlined referral mechanisms and inclusion of private facilities. The government responded by stating that under the Ayushman Bharat scheme the major corporate hospitals and private hospitals have been empanelled on an insurance scheme.	Ayushman Bharat	Even though the issue of inclusion of private facilities were addressed, the issue of training of frontline healthcare staff and physicians to ‘red flags of cancer’ are essentials and such training must be included for hospital accreditation process of NABH (National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers) and NQAS (National Quality Assurance Standards) so that it is integrated into the day-to-day processes of hospitals and the hospital in incentivised in training its staff. Frontline health workers must be better incentivised so that they can be retained at primary level care institutions.
11	2.11.1	The committee stressed the need for integration of diagnostics and treatment and smooth linkages between the two, to which the government stated that the common identifier ABHA ID (Ayushman Bharat Health Account Identifier) and the comprehensive primary healthcare integrates screening, prevention, control, and management of NCDs, and this is further strengthened through the community-based assessment checklist.	Recordkeeping	The comprehensiveness and linkages of various programs can be achieved through a common identifier. This must be linked to the existing unique identification number (Aadhar number) so that there is less duplicity of patient identifiers. The database sharing, well protected and private, must be enabled for sharing by the patients’ consent across diagnostic and treatment facilities.
12	2.13.1	The committee recommended that the work done by National Institute of Cancer Prevention and Research (or NICPR) must be widely published and placed in the public domain with	Awareness	The publication of research must be translated into the various languages that are available in India and the medium for the

		which the government agreed and stated that the same is already being done.		message needs to be diversified for it to be accessible to a wide variety of populations, as not all parts of the population may be scientifically educated/technically savvy. Information Education and Communication (IEC) materials should be tested to work for rural as well as urban populations. It can also include other forms of media such as movies, plays, documentaries, etc. Some awareness steps taken from the polio program can be used.
1 3	2.13.2	The committee recommended that the NICPR should strengthen training and screening, awareness, and prevention activities to which the government gave an affirmative response.	Awareness	Training is important especially where cases may be missed or underreported. This is even more relevant as many occupational cancers may not be properly diagnosed and not be reported under the required reporting mechanism which could lead to prevention.
1 4	2.13.3	The committee recommended the identification of SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity and Threat analysis) for NICPR so its cancer prevention mandate can be met. The ministry highlighted the work done by NICPR.	Awareness	The role of NICPR is laudable and this must be expanded.
<i>Summary of recommendations which the committee does not desire to pursue in view of MoHFW replies.</i>				
1 5	1.5.7	The committee recommended cancer to be made a notifiable disease as non-notification may result in underreporting and,	Recordkeeping	This is something that can be questioned as making cancer notifiable has been recommended by the Indian Council of Medical Research (National Centre for
1 6	1.5.8	the committee noted that when recording mortality, a cancer death is often wrongfully recorded as cardio-respiratory failure.		

		This must be rectified. The committee suggested recordkeeping of mortality with a web-based reporting portal. The ministry denied the need for making cancer notifiable stating that cancer is non communicable and does not have community spread and cannot be made notifiable in the present circumstances.		Disease Informatics Research) itself and the rationale of cancer being non-communicable does not concur in the case of cervical cancer as it is linked to infection with high-risk HPV, an extremely common virus transmitted through sexual contact. Cervical cancer being one of the three high incidence sites of cancer in India (and it is also one of the three screened cancers). The strengthening of the registry has been done in developed countries and has shown positive results in terms of focussed screening. ⁹
1 7	1.6.3	The committee noted the high use of tobacco and alcohol in the Northeastern states. Tobacco consumption there being 60% (compared to national prevalence of 28%) and alcohol prevalence being 28% (compared to 12% national prevalence). The risk of cancer from alcohol, the committee stated, is confirmed and it was noted that it becomes higher when tobacco is consumed with alcohol.	Tobacco Cessation	This issue needs more focus as tobacco and alcohol have other socio-economic and health issues which lead to a high burden on society. Such work should be undertaken in a potentially and culturally sensitive manner.
1 8	1.6.5	The committee highlighted the use of pan masala (or betel quid), which the committee noted contained tobacco with or without Areca nut. The committee noted that 80% of tobacco consumption is in the form of chewing tobacco. The committee also recommended that indirect advertisement of pan masala should be stopped. The government replied that under the food safety regulations, there is a prohibition on tobacco and	Tobacco Cessation	The issue through regulation may have been resolved, but the regulation needs to be notified, or re-issued each year by state governments in some cases, instead of it being a perpetual regulation. Further, it is often seen that street vendors now sell non-packaged tobacco along with tobacco free

		nicotine in food products. The government stated that the food regulator has communicated to states to enforce the ban on gutkha (a type of chewable, smokeless betel quid with multiple ingredients including tobacco) and chewing tobacco.		pan masala which the consumers manually mix. This tobacco is made by the unorganised sector and needs to be regulated through inspection drives and flying squads with the help of the police.
19	1.6.6	The committee noted that since oral cancer due to tobacco leads to the highest contribution of cases, there is need for implementing the COTPA Act as the Nation Health policy has set out to reduce prevalence of tobacco use by 30% by 2025. The committee further suggested that designated smoking areas at public places and smoke-free policy in organisations must be implemented. The ministry stated that the government had initiated a draft regulation towards this.	Tobacco Cessation	The COTPA Act needs to be made more stringent as the current penalties may be minimal for smoking in public places and in and around educational institutes. There should be stronger implementation of tobacco cessation for teenagers and younger persons.
20	1.7.6	The committee suggested that research looking into causative factors of gender specific cancer at specific sites must be performed to which the government agreed.	Recordkeeping	A better understanding of cancer causation is linked to cancer data which is linked to robust recordkeeping. This is possible by strengthening the National Cancer Registry Program for which making cancer notifiable may be an important step.
21	1.8.3	The committee noted that the rise in cancer incidence will increase from 8 lakhs (800,000) in 2018 to 13 lakhs (1,300,000) in 2035 and noted the stark difference in cancer incidence ratio in India being 0.68 as compared to very high human development index countries (0.38) and high HDI countries (0.57). The committee stated that this could be attributed to unequal distribution and lack of access to health care resources across India.	Recordkeeping	The first step to understanding incidence is proper recordkeeping which will then enable the actual investigation of causative factors and will enable the distribution and resource allocation for prevention. The focus needs to be on prevention as that will lead to a lower economic burden in terms of future medical bills instead of the current

				revenue that may be generated by use of Group 1 carcinogens like tobacco, and asbestos, among others.
2 2	2.3.4	The committee noted that 50% of cancers are tobacco-related and stated that more effort must be made to campaign against tobacco consumption, to which the government replied that the national tobacco control program is being implemented, the COTPA Act exists and the Juvenile Justice Act makes selling tobacco to minor a stringent offence with major punishment.	Tobacco Cessation	The COTPA Act needs to be made more stringent as the current penalties may be minimal for smoking in public places, in and around educational institutes and for tobacco cessation efforts for teenagers and youngsters. The efforts of the government must translate to a reduction in tobacco use. Non-Governmental organisations (or NGOs) can be involved.
2 3	2.5.4	The committee stressed screening beyond oral, breast and cervical cancers not only for prevention, but for early diagnosis. The committee also suggested centrally sponsored screening programs, to which the government stated that the Ayushman Bharat clinics under the National Programme for Prevention and Control of Non-Communicable Diseases, or NP-NCD are being implemented.	Screening	Though screening is a pertinent tool, it must be beyond the three sites selected currently (oral, breast and cervical). Further, more than early diagnosis, the focus must be on prevention which is possible by stopping the use of carcinogens like tobacco, asbestos and dietary sources which are attributed to cancer aetiology. It is likely that the revenue generated by use of carcinogens will be more than offset by higher medical bills in the future without prevention.
2 4	2.5.5	The committee stressed screening and suggested that screening become country-wide & population-based instead of opportunity-based as currently exists. The committee suggested that efforts like ones done in the polio program must be	Screening	The need for linking screening to the recordkeeping is appropriate as hotspots can be identified and the focus areas for policy action can be stressed. The polio program's

		undertaken for cancer screening and the data generated should be linked with the cancer registry program.		marketing and outreach efforts must be replicated for the cancer screening program. The need for incentivising screening and increasing the scope is in the right direction as long as it prevents over diagnosis and covers vulnerable and high-risk populations.
2 5	2.5.6	The committee suggested marginal concessions in insurance for those individuals who undertook cancer screening as an incentive. This was forwarded to the Department of Financial Services which stated that this can be further examined by the insurance industry.	Financial Incentive	The marginal concessions in insurance and incentivising pocket-spent money on cancer screening and preventive diagnosis must be done by provided tax incentives for tax paying individuals. A regulatory role of the government, instead of fully depending on response from the insurance industry, may be useful.
2 6	2.7.6	The committee stressed decentralisation of cancer diagnostic and capping out-of-pocket fees for diagnostic tests. The ministry stated that this is being done with a price list as the CGHS or the Central Government Health Scheme and is covered by Ayushman Bharat empanelled in-patient hospitals.	Financial Incentive	This can be linked to universal health access and the diagnostic fee capping may be linked with tax incentives for undergoing screening for earning individuals and similar provisions through welfare schemes for others who may not be able to afford them.
2 7	2.8.1	The committee stressed implementation of the Operational Framework: Management of Common Cancers to be undertaken and the relevant parameters to be included in periodic surveys including the National Family Health Survey, National Sample Survey Organisation and District Level Household Surveys.	Recordkeeping	This must be seen in the broader context of cancer recordkeeping and must be integrated so that data flows from one sector/agency/ministry to another and health determinants can inform diagnosis and aetiology-based research.

<i>Summary of recommendations regarding replies of MoHFW which have not been accepted by the committee and further recommendations have been suggested.</i>				
28	1.5.2	The limited coverage of 10-16% by the NCRP program was highlighted and a need for policy formulation on realistic information on the incidence and types of cancers was highlighted. The committee reiterated that the ministry should persuade all state governments to participate in cancer registries so that 100% of the Indian population can be covered under PBCR. New states that have started cancer atlases was highlighted including Andhra Odisha, Uttarakhand, and Rajasthan.	Recordkeeping	This addresses the core issue of cancer recordkeeping. The persuasion of all state governments will be very tangible when a legal backing is issued to the states by the MoHFW to make cancer notifiable.
29	1.5.4	The issue of cancer record-keeping was raised so that an unbiased cancer registry can be created. The committee reiterated that the Ayushman Bharat digital mission and population-based cancer registries should be linked to reduce duplicity and to get real time data on cancer related illnesses.	Recordkeeping	The issue of recordkeeping is critical since without proper incidence, mortality, and morbidity data the right focus on groups of people with link to various geographical areas cannot be undertaken. Making cancer notifiable makes recordkeeping a mandate and the accountability shifts to every medical practitioner. This must be complemented by easy, legally sound and hassle free reporting and notification processes for hospitals and medical practitioners.
30	1.5.5	The issue of taxing tobacco products was reiterated by the committee which stated that tobacco products must be taxed at the highest possible level to disincentivise their use as tobacco	Tobacco Cessation	The issue of tobacco needs to be highlighted in all ways, beyond tax disincentivising. There must be regulation which provides stringent punishment in the case of COTPA

		is a leading cause of cancer. This was concurred by the MoHFW.		Act violations and currently, the law may be “toothless” with a paltry penalty for smoking in public places of Rs 200 (1-2 USD)
3 2	1.6.7	The committee highlighted the need for strong screening mechanisms. The government stated that screening is being done at Ayushman wellness centres for oral, breast and cervical cancers. The committee suggested that this must be done at a mass movement level with one day per month to be dedicated for cancer screening and a ‘Jan Andolan’ or ‘people’s movement’ should be undertaken.	Screening/ Awarenes s	The mass movement will be possible when there is mass awareness. This requires the level of involvement such as in the case of the polio program where awareness drives using celebrities were involved and there was dedicated on-the-ground presence of polio staff convincing people for the need of polio vaccination. This can also be done by involving NGOs.
3 3	1.8.2	The committee flagged the lack of cancer mortality data, as there is a lack of a well-defined system to record cancer deaths. The Ministry stated that the software used by the state of Tamil Nadu may be adopted by NCDIR which the committee stated must be customised as per other states’ requirements.	Recordkee ping	This addresses the larger issue of cancer recordkeeping. The National Cancer Registry program must be enhanced with a war footing with there being a legal mandate to report cancer cases and cancer mortality which can be achieved by making it notifiable.

Declarations

No external funding has been received for this work. Consent, ethics requirement: Not applicable as it is a review of a report in the public domain. The study involved no human participants, animals or human tissue. There are no conflicts of interests reported. The paper has been posted as a preprint on Zenodo in April 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15180565>)

References

1. Department-Related Parliamentary Standing Committee on Health and Family Welfare. *One Hundred Thirty Ninth Report on Cancer Care Plan & Management: Prevention, Diagnosis, Research & Affordability of Cancer Treatment*. Rajya Sabha Secretariat, Parliament of India; 2022.
2. Sathishkumar K, Chaturvedi M, Das P, Stephen S, Mathur P. Cancer incidence estimates for 2022 & projection for 2025: Result from National Cancer Registry Programme, India. *Indian J Med Res*. 2022;156(4 & 5):598-607. doi:10.4103/ijmr.ijmr_1821_22
3. *Parliamentary Committees*. Accessed March 18, 2025. <https://web.archive.org/web/20120724034114/http://www.parliamentofindia.nic.in/ls/intr o/p21.htm>
4. Department-Related Parliamentary Standing Committee on Health and Family Welfare. *147th Report on Action Taken by Government on the Recommendations/Observations Contained in the 139th Report on the "Cancer Care Plan & Management: Prevention, Diagnosis, Research & Affordability of Cancer Treatment"*. Rajya Sabha Secretariat, Parliament of India; 2023. Accessed February 10, 2025. https://sansad.in/getFile/rsnew/Committee_site/Committee_File/ReportFile/14/168/147_2023_8_16.pdf?source=rajyasabha
5. National Health Authority, Government of India. About PM-JAY - National Health Authority | GOI. Accessed March 4, 2025. <https://nha.gov.in/PM-JAY>
6. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. *Operational Framework Management of Common Cancers*.; 2016. Accessed March 4, 2025. <https://nhsrcindia.org/sites/default/files/2021-03/Operational%20Framework%20Management%20of%20Common%20Cancers.pdf>
7. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. *National Health Policy 2017*.; 2017. Accessed March 4, 2025. <https://mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/9147562941489753121.pdf>

8. Singh R, Frank AL. Need for Making Cancer a Notifiable Disease in India. Published online February 17, 2025. doi:10.32388/IL4JV0.2
9. Chaturvedi M, Nath A, Mathur P. Cancer registration in India: Current status and the road ahead. *Ann Oncol Res Ther.* 2023;3(2):55-56. doi:10.4103/aort.aort_13_23
10. Singh R, Frank AL. Analysis of mesothelioma cases and National Cancer Registry data to assess asbestos exposure in India. *Public Health Action.* 2024;14(1):30-33. doi:10.5588/pha.24.0003
11. Singh R, Frank AL. Notification and recordkeeping of occupational mesothelioma in India. Published online February 15, 2025. doi:10.1101/2025.02.11.25322115
12. Singh R, Frank AL. Analysis of the Indian Government's position on the use of asbestos and its health effects. *Public Health Action.* 2023;13(2):50-52. doi:10.5588/pha.23.0013
13. Cervical Cancer Causes, Risk Factors, and Prevention - NCI. October 13, 2022. Accessed March 4, 2025. <https://www.cancer.gov/types/cervical/causes-risk-prevention>
14. Cervical cancer. Accessed March 19, 2025. <https://www.who.int/health-topics/cervical-cancer>
15. Government of India. *The Cigarettes and Other Tobacco Products (Prohibition of Advertisement and Regulation of Trade and Commerce, Production, Supply and Distribution) Act, 2003.*; 2003. Accessed February 14, 2023. <https://legislative.gov.in/sites/default/files/A2003-34.pdf>
16. Singh R. Decentralisation of the Compliance of Anti-tobacco Law in India: The Case of Higher Educational Institutions in New Delhi, India. *Cureus.* Published online July 1, 2023. doi:10.7759/cureus.41247
17. Chemicals in Meat Cooked at High Temperatures and Cancer Risk - NCI. April 2, 2018. Accessed March 4, 2025. <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/causes-prevention/risk/diet/cooked-meats-fact-sheet>